

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF NANOGEL CONTAINING COMBINATION OF CLINDAMYCIN AND TRETINOIN FOR TOPICAL DELIVERY

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ABSTRACT

This study presents the evaluation of Clindamycin and Tretinoin for a nanosponge-based topical gel formulation. Nanosponges loaded with the drugs showed white, solid appearances with mild odor. Particle sizes ranged from 55.85 nm to 100.00 nm; F3 had the smallest size (55.85 nm) and highest entrapment efficiency (95.72%). Zeta potential values between -10.6 mV and -14.0 mV indicated moderate colloidal stability. SEM imaging confirmed spherical, porous structures suitable for drug encapsulation. The optimized nanosponge formulation was incorporated into a gel, which was semisolid, yellowish, and homogeneous, with a pH of 5.9 and viscosity of 3416 ± 0.26 cps. It showed good spreadability (19.78 gm·cm/sec) and no skin irritation. *In vitro* drug release studies showed sustained release over 14 hours, with F3 achieving the highest cumulative release (96.28%). Kinetic modeling confirmed a Higuchi release profile ($R^2 = 0.9953$), suggesting diffusion-controlled release. Antimicrobial activity showed dose-dependent inhibition of *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, with greater activity at higher concentrations. Stability studies over 90 days showed no significant changes in pH or viscosity under accelerated conditions, confirming formulation stability. Overall, the nanosponge gel system offers a promising strategy for topical delivery of Clindamycin and Tretinoin.

Keywords: Clindamycin, Tretinoin, Nanosponge, Gel formulation, FTIR, UV spectroscopy, Drug release, stability study.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nanogels have emerged as suitable vehicle for delivering and releasing medications to patients in recent years as one of the many dimensions of nanomedicine—the junction of nanotechnology, medicine, and pharmaceuticals. Nanogels are crosslinked polymer networks that are nanoscale in size and capable of absorbing enormous amounts of water (Sivaram *et al.*, 2015). Nanogels are hydrogels with a size of nanometers or less. A hydrogel is a polymer-based gel that is made by connecting polymer chains to form a macromolecular network. Hydrogels can be made in a variety of ways, but all require the creation of polymeric monomers, which must then be polymerized with functional cross-linker molecules to form a ‘net-like’ polymer structure (Neamtu *et al.*, 2017).

Tretinoin, also known as all-transretinoic acid (ATRA), is a naturally occurring derivative of vitamin A (retinol) that act by binding to two nuclear receptor families within keratinocytes: the retinoic acid receptors (RAR) and the retinoid X receptors (RXR) (Zhu, 2019). It is a medication used for the treatment of acne and acute promyelocytic leukemia. Tretinoin (along with other retinoids) is vitamin A it is in the retinoid family of medications (Molin and Ruzicka, 2019).

Clindamycin, among the commonly used topical antibiotics for acne vulgaris, has shown to be more effective over time. Clindamycin also contains anti-inflammatory characteristics, which are expected to play a key role in its anti-acne therapeutic effects. The efficacy of topical antimicrobial medicines is affected by the concentration of the medication in the pilosebaceous ducts (Han *et al.*, 2018). Furthermore, the formation of resistance is linked to low and fluctuating drug concentrations in the pilosebaceous ducts. The reliable drug delivery systems that allow for improved drug penetration can improve efficacy while also preventing the development of resistance (Ezike *et al.*, 2023).

The goal of this study was to statistically optimise the formulation and evaluation of Nanogel containing combination of Clindamycin and Tretinoin for topical delivery which was a successful option for acne treatment.

2. METHODS AND MATERIAL

2.1 Chemicals

Methyl paraben, Propylene glycol, Disodium hydrogen phosphate, Potassium dihydrogen phosphate, and Sodium chloride were obtained from Merck, a reputable supplier of analytical reagents. Rankem provided the Methanol, and Sulab provided the Carbopol 934. Loba provided the Triethanolamine. Compound W provided the Tretinoin.

2.2 Pre-formulation studies

Pre-formulation studies are first step in drug development, where the basic properties of a drug are examined. These comprise its stability, pH, melting point, solubility, and compatibility with other ingredients. This helps scientists choose the right formulation method and ensures the drug will be safe, effective, and stable in final form (Ahirwar and Shukla, 2023).

2.2.1 Organoleptic Properties

Organoleptic properties of a drug refer to its sensory characteristics, such as color, odor, taste, and appearance (Bilous and Kovalevska 2019).

2.2.2 Solubility study

To perform solubility study of Clindamycin and Tretinoin by visual inspection, a small, fixed amount of each drug is added to different solvents (e.g., water, ethanol, methanol, acetone, DMSO) in separate test tubes. The mixtures are shaken or stirred at room temperature for a specific time, usually 10–15 minutes. After settling, each tube is visually inspected for clarity or undissolved particles. A clear solution indicates good solubility, slight cloudiness or partial settling suggests limited solubility, and visible undissolved drug confirms poor solubility. This simple method gives a qualitative assessment of solubility (Malaekheh-Nikouei *et al.*, 2011).

2.2.3 pH determination

To determine the pH of Clindamycin and Tretinoin using a digital pH meter, prepare separate solutions or dispersions of each drug in a suitable solvent or buffer (commonly distilled water or ethanol-water mixture) (Wagner *et al.*, 2003).

2.2.4 Melting Point

To determine melting point of Clindamycin and Tretinoin using melting point apparatus, first ensure both drug samples are finely powdered and dry (Mao, *et al.*, 2016).

2.2.5 Determination of λ max and calibration curve

- **Preparation of standard stock solution:**

About 5 mg of Clindamycin and 5 mg of Tretinoin were precisely weighed and each transferred separately into 5 ml volumetric flasks. The volume in each flask was made up to 5 ml using their respective solvents to prepare solutions with concentration of 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. From each of these stock solutions, 1 ml was pipetted and further diluted to 10 ml using methanol to acquire standard stock solutions of Clindamycin and Tretinoin, each with final concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (Kokilambigai *et al.*, 2017).

- **λ max**

From the previously prepared stock solutions of Clindamycin and Tretinoin, 1 ml of each sample was transferred separately into 5 ml volumetric flasks. The volume in each flask was made up to the mark using methanol to achieve a final concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. These samples were then scanned using a UV-VIS spectrophotometer in the wavelength range of 200–800 nm, with methanol used as the blank. The wavelengths corresponding to the maximum absorbance (λ max) for Clindamycin and Tretinoin were determined from the scan results.

- **Linearity**

Aliquots of 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, and 14 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ were prepared from the 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ Clindamycin standard solution, and the same concentration range 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, and 14 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ was prepared from the 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ Tretinoin standard solution. These aliquots were accurately transferred into a series of 5 ml volumetric flasks and diluted to the mark with methanol. The absorbance of each solution was measured at 210.0 nm for Clindamycin and 357.0 nm for Tretinoin using methanol as the blank. A six-point calibration curve was then constructed for each drug by plotting absorbance against concentration, covering a range from 4–12 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The absorbance response for both medications was discovered to be linear within this range. The linear regression equation for Clindamycin was $y = 0.0552x + 0.127$ with a correlation coefficient R^2 of 0.9994, and for Tretinoin, the equation was $y = 0.0315x + 0.0063$ with an R^2 of 0.9998, indicating excellent linearity for both compounds (Kumbhar and Salunkhe 2016).

2.2.6 Fourier transmission Infra-Red Spectroscopy

The FT-IR spectra of Tretinoin and Clindamycin was recorded in the range of 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} using the KBr pellet method with an FT-IR spectrophotometer. A KBr disc was prepared by mixing 1 mg of each Clindamycin and Tretinoin with 100 mg of spectroscopic-grade KBr, which was dried using an IR lamp. The drug and KBr mixture was subjected to hydraulic pressure to form a disc. This disc was then placed in the FT-IR chamber, and the infrared spectrum was recorded over the 4000–400 cm^{-1} range (Barros 2015).

2.3 Preparation of Clindamycin and Tretinoin -loaded nanosponges

Beta-cyclodextrin Nanosponges were made by 'hot melt method'. Various ratios comprising Diphenyl carbonate (DPC cross-linker) and Beta- cyclodextrin (β -CD polymer) (Ratios of DPC and β -CD are given in table no.4) were chosen for the nanosponges preparation. For one to three hours, the finely homogenized anhydrous polymer (β -CD) and crosslinker (DPC) were heated gradually to 90 to 100 oC while being stirred by a magnetic device. The substrate solution (β -CD and DMC) was set aside for 1 to 3 hours to finish the cross-linking reactions, which produced nanosponges. After that, the resulting reaction mixture was left to cool to ambient temperature. To remove unmodified β -CD, the sample underwent multiple washings with twice-distilled water. After being dried at 40 °C, the resulting placebo nanosponges were kept in a desiccator until needed again (Penjuri SC 2016).

2.3.1 Drug load in Placebo nanosponges

Placebo NS (1 gm) was distributed in 50 mL of double-distilled water using a magnetic stirrer. About 100:50 mg of Drugs (Tretinoin and clindamycin) was included into the aforesaid dispersion. The resulting suspensions were centrifuged for 10 minutes at 2000 rpm in order to extract the drug that had become entrapped as a residue below the very colloidal supernatant. Following that, lyophilization of the supernatant was carried out at -81 °C and 0.0010 mbar of force. The dried NS powder that was laced with drugs was kept for later use (Sharma R 2011)

Table 1: Composition of Nanosponges formulation

Formulations Code	Beta-cyclodextrin-Polymer (mg) X1	Diphenyl carbonate-Cross linker (DPC) (mg) X2	Distilled water (ml)	Stirring time (hrs) X3	Drug (2:1 Ratio) (100:50 mg)	Temperature (°C)
F1	100	50	100	1-3	150	90 to 100
F2	150	100	100	1-3	150	90 to 100
F3	200	150	100	1-3	150	90 to 100
F4	250	200	100	1-3	150	90 to 100
F5	300	250	100	1-3	150	90 to 100

2.4 Characterization of Clindamycin and Tretinoin –loaded Nanosponge

2.4.1 Physical appearance of drug loaded Nanosponge

The physical appearance of nanosponges can be assessed by simple visual inspection, noting characteristics such as color, texture, uniformity, and presence of any clumps or phase separation (Gedam and Basarkar 2021).

2.4.2 Particle size of drug loaded Nanosponge

Nanosponges' particle size was measured using a Malvern Zetasizer (Abbas *et al.*, 2018).

2.4.3 Zeta potential of drug loaded Nanosponge

The zeta potential of nanosponges was measured using a Malvern Zetasizer (Darandale and Vavia 2013).

2.4.4 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

The surface morphology of drug-loaded nanosponges was examined using a scanning electron microscope (SEM). Prior to imaging, the samples were coated with a thin metallic layer typically between 2 to 20 nanometers thick using a sputter coater under vacuum conditions. Electrons scattered at a 90° angle during interaction between the beam and the atoms on the sample surface were selectively captured. These signals were then processed to

produce high-resolution surface topography images, following principles derived from Rutherford's and Kramer's laws (Allahyari *et al.*, 2020).

2.4.5 Entrapment efficiency

To assess entrapment efficiency, 10 mL of Clindamycin and Tretinoin-loaded nanosponges were properly measured and transferred to a volumetric flask containing 5 mL of methanol. To ensure that the medication was completely extracted, the liquid was vortexed for one minute. The volume was then reduced to 10 mL with methanol, and the solution thoroughly mixed. A UV-Visible spectrophotometer was used to determine the concentration of the entrapped Clindamycin and Tretinoin following filtering and adequate dilution (Manyam *et al.*, 2013).

$$\% EE = \frac{\text{Initial amount of drug added} - \text{Drug amount in supernatant}}{\text{Initial amount of drug added}} \times 100$$

2.5 Preparation of Nanogel formulation

Initially, 50 ml of warm water (A) were used to submerge carbopol-934 for two hours, and a magnetic stirrer operating at 600 rpm was used to spread it evenly. In another vessel, the carboxymethyl cellulose and methyl paraben were combined with 50 ml of room temperature water (B) and stirred continuously until they formed a firm polymer. Both mixes A and B were stirred continuously. At this point, they included the permeability booster propylene glycol. Once the ultimate dispersion was determined, a smooth, lump-free gel was generated.

Table: 2 Composition of Nanosponges Gel

Name of Ingredient	Formulation I
Carbopol 940	1000 mg
Carboxymethyl cellulose	1000 mg
Propylene glycol	500 μ l
Methyl paraben	200 μ l
Nanosponges	1000 mg
Triethanolamine	q.s
Water	100 ml

2.6 Characterization of drug loaded Nanogel formulation

2.6.1 Physical appearance of drug loaded Nanogel formulation

The physical appearance of the nanosponges gel formulation was evaluated by visual observation under natural light (Iriverenti *et al.*, 2020).

2.6.2 Viscosity determination of drug loaded Nanogel formulation

A Brookfield viscometer was used to assess the drug-loaded nanogel formulation's viscosity (Sujitha and Muzib 2019).

2.6.3 pH determination of drug loaded Nanogel formulation

A calibrated digital pH meter was used to measure the drug-loaded nanogel formulation's pH (Kharwade 2023).

2.6.4 Spreadability determination of drug loaded Nanogel formulation

The spreadability of the drug-loaded nanosponges gel (nanogel) formulation was evaluated using the glass slide method. 50 mg of gel was placed between two glass slides, and a known weight was applied on the upper slide for a specific time. This test helps assess the ease with which the gel can be applied to the skin surface, with better spreadability indicating improved patient compliance and uniform application (Sivadasan *et al.*, 2024).

$$S = M \times L / T$$

Where, S-Spread ability, g.cm/s M-Weight put on the upper glass L-Length of glass slide T-Time for spreading gel in sec.

2.6.5 Skin irritation test of drug loaded Nanogel formulation

The skin irritation test of the drug-loaded nanogel formulation was conducted on one healthy Wistar rat average weight 150– 200 g was used with following ethical guidelines. A small area on the dorsal side of the rat was shaved 24 hours prior to the test. The site was observed at regular intervals (e.g., 1, 24, 48, and 72 hours) for signs of irritation such as redness, swelling, or inflammation. The reaction was scored based on a standard dermal irritation scale to assess the formulation's skin compatibility (Srivastava *et al.*, 2021).

2.6.6 Drug Release Study

The *in-vitro* drug release study of Clindamycin and Tretinoin-loaded nanogel was conducted using the dialysis bag diffusion method. A specific amount of the prepared formulation was placed inside a dialysis membrane and immersed in a beaker containing 100 ml of phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). The setup was maintained at a constant temperature of 37 ± 2 °C and stirred continuously at 100 rpm using a magnetic stirrer to simulate physiological conditions. To maintain sink conditions, 2 ml samples were taken out of the release medium at prearranged intervals and promptly replaced with an equivalent volume of brand-new phosphate buffer.

To understand the release behavior of Clindamycin and Tretinoin from the nanosponges, the drug release data were fitted into various kinetic models. These included the zero-order model, which assumes a constant release rate independent of drug concentration; the first-order model, where the release rate is concentration-dependent; and the Higuchi model, which explains drug release from a matrix system as a diffusion-controlled process, proportional to the square root of time (Banjare *et al.*, 2020).

2.7 Antimicrobial activity

2.7.1 Preparation of Nutrient Agar Media

To prepare the nutrient media, 2.8 g of nutrient powder was accurately weighed and dissolved in 100 ml of distilled water. The pH of the solution was measured and adjusted, if necessary, before sterilization. The prepared media was then sterilized using an autoclave at 121 °C and 15 psi pressure for 15 minutes. After sterilization, the hot nutrient media was poured into sterile Petri dishes under a laminar airflow cabinet and left undisturbed until the agar solidified completely (Devika *et al.*, 2021).

2.7.2 Well Diffusion Assay

The bacterial suspension of *S.aureus* was standardized to 10^8 CFU/ml of bacteria and kept into the shaker. Using a micropipette, 100 μ l of the broth's inoculums (108 CFU/ml) were then transferred to a new, sterile, solidified Agar Media Plate. A well diffusion assay was performed against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* in order to assess the antibacterial efficacy of the nanogel formulation loaded with clindamycin and retinoin was prepared, sterilized, and poured into sterile Petri plates, then allowed to solidify. The antimicrobial effectiveness of the gel formulation against the test organisms was evaluated by measuring the zones of inhibition surrounding each well in millimeters (Baskaran *et al.*, 2012).

2.8 Stability studies

The drug-loaded nanogel formulation was packed and placed in a stability chamber for accelerated stability testing as per ICH guidelines. The samples were stored under two conditions: $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ with $60 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity, and $40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ with $70 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity, for duration of three months. At regular intervals—specifically on days 30, 45, 60, and 90—the formulation was evaluated for changes in key parameters such as viscosity and pH. These assessments were carried out to monitor the physical stability of the gel and ensure that its quality and performance remained consistent over time under stressed storage conditions (Kaur *et al.*, 2020).

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Pre-formulation study of drug

3.1.1 Organoleptic properties of Clindamycin and Tretinoin

Table 3: Organoleptic properties of Clindamycin and Tretinoin

Drug	Organoleptic properties	Clindamycin	Tretinoin
Clindamycin and Tretinoin	Color	White to off-white	Yellow to pale yellow
	Odor	Odorless	Floral odor
	Appearance	Crystalline powder	Powder
	State	Solid	Solid powder

3.1.2 Solubility study

Table 4: Solubility study of Clindamycin and Tretinoin

Drugs	Solvents	Clindamycin	Tretinoin
Clindamycin and Tretinoin	Water	Freely soluble	Soluble
	Ethanol	Freely soluble	Freely soluble
	Methanol	Freely soluble	Freely soluble
	Chloroform	Practically insoluble	Soluble
	DMSO	Freely soluble	Freely soluble

3.1.3 pH and Melting Point

Table 5: pH and Melting Point determination

Drugs	Observed (pH)	Observed (Melting Point)	Reference for melting point
Clindamycin	3.5	142°C	141-143°C
Tretinoin	6.3	180 °C	179-182 °C

3.1.4 λ max

Table 6: Lambda max of Clindamycin and Tretinoin

Drugs	Lambda max of Clindamycin	Lambda max of Tretinoin	Center point (Both Drug)
Clindamycin and Tretinoin	210.0 nm	357.0 nm	265.0 nm

3.1.5 Calibration curve of both drugs

3.1.5.1 Calibration curve of Clindamycin and Tretinoin

Graph 1: Calibration curve of Clindamycin

Graph 2: Calibration curve of Tretinoin

3.1.7 Functional group identified by Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) study

3.1.7.1 FTIR of Clindamycin

Graph 3: FTIR of Clindamycin

Table 7: Interpretation of IR spectrum of Clindamycin

Peak obtained	Reference peak	Functional group	Name of functional group
3383.41	3400-3300	N-H Stretch	Aliphatic primary amine
1673.88	1690-1640	C=N Stretch	Imine / oxime
1307.86	1310-1250	C-O Stretch	Aromatic ester
1254.07	1275-1200	C-O Stretch	Alkyl aryl ether
1080.68	1085-1050	C-O Stretch	Primary alcohol

3.1.7.2. FTIR of Tretinoin

Graph 4: FTIR of Tretinoin

Table 8: Interpretation of IR spectrum of Tretinoin

Peak obtained	Reference peak	Functional group	Name of functional group
3440.33	3500- 3400	N-H Stretching	Primary Amine
2929.55	3000-2840	C-H Stretching	Alkane
1632.19	1662-1626	C=C Stretching	Alkene
1250.25	1275-1200	C-O Stretching	Alkyl aryl ether
1110.97	1124-1087	C-O Stretching	Secondary alcohol

3.2. Evaluation parameter of Clindamycin and Tretinoin loaded nanosponge’s formulation

3.2.1 Physical Appearance of Nanosponges

Table 9: Physical Appearance of Clindamycin and Tretinoin loaded nanosponges

Formulation	Parameters	Observation
Nanosponges	Colour	White
	Odour	Mild Characteristic
	Appearance	Solid

3.2.2 Particle Size

Graph 5: Particle size (F1)

Graph 6: Particle size (F2)

Graph 7: Particle size (F3)

Graph 8: Particle size (F4)

Graph 9: Particle size (F5)

3.2.3 Zeta potential

Graph 10: Zeta potential (F1)

Graph 11: Zeta potential (F2)

Graph 12: Zeta potential (F3)

Graph 13: Zeta potential (F4)

Graph 14: Zeta potential (F5)

Graph 15: graphical representation of Zeta potential and particle size of nanosponges

3.2.4 Entrapment efficacy of Clindamycin and Tretinoin loaded nanosponges

Table 10: Zeta potential, particle size and Entrapment efficacy (%) of Clindamycin and Tretinoin loaded nanosponges formulation

Formulation Code	Zeta potential mV	Particle size (nm)	Entrapment efficacy (%)
Nanosponges F1	-10.6mV	100.00 nm	83.53
Nanosponges F2	-11.3 mV	69.70nm	79.22
Nanosponges F3	-14.0 mV	55.85nm	95.72
Nanosponges F4	-11.6 mV	85.76nm	81.38
Nanosponges F5	-11.3 mV	93.55nm	88.65

3.2.5 Scanning electron microscope (SEM)

Figure 1: Scanning electron microscope (SEM)

3.3 Evaluation parameter of Clindamycin and Tretinoin loaded nanosponges gel formulation

3.3.1 Organoleptic properties nano gel formulation

Table 11: Organoleptic properties nano gel formulation

Parameters	Results
Physical appearance	Semisolid gel
Colour	Slightly yellowish gel
Homogeneity	Absence of aggregates

3.3.2 Determination of Viscosity, pH, Skin irritation study, skin irritation test and Spreadability test

Table 12: Viscosity, pH, Skin irritation study, skin irritation test and Spreadability test of gel formulation

Formulation	Results (pH)	Viscosity Results (cps)	Spreadability test (gm.cm/sec)	skin irritation test
Drugs loaded nan gel formulation	5.9	3416±0.26	19.78	Not irritant observed

3.3.3 *In-vitro* drug release study of F1 to F5 formulations

Table 13: Cumulative % drug released

Time (hrs.)	Cumulative % drug released				
	Formulation 1	Formulation 2	Formulation 3	Formulation 4	Formulation 5
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	12.11	21.80	22.18	15.74	13.86
2	26.64	34.62	39.17	29.55	27.36
4	40.03	43.68	48.23	38.28	37.46
6	60.35	57.30	60.75	48.33	48.33
8	69.23	66.53	69.38	57.36	59.62
10	73.15	73.77	78.09	66.10	78.50
12	88.63	79.32	88.55	80.71	88.85
14	91.74	84.6	96.28	90.04	87.36

Graph 16: Release study of all formulation (F1 to F5)

Table 14: Release kinetics study of F3 formulation

Time (Hr)	cumulative % drug released	% drug remaining	Square root time	log Cumu % drug remaining	log time	log Cumu % drug released
0	0	100	0.000	2.000	0.000	0.000
1	22.18	77.82	1.000	1.891	0.000	1.346
2	39.17	60.83	1.414	1.784	0.301	1.593
4	48.23	51.77	2.000	1.714	0.602	1.683
6	60.75	39.25	2.449	1.594	0.778	1.784
8	69.38	30.62	2.828	1.486	0.903	1.841
10	78.09	21.91	3.162	1.341	1.000	1.893
12	88.55	11.45	3.464	1.059	1.079	1.947
14	96.28	3.72	3.742	0.571	1.146	1.984

Table 15: Interpretation of R-square values and rate constants of release kinetics of Nano gel (Correlation value (R2 value))

Formulation	Model	Kinetic parameter values
Nano gel	Zero Order	$R^2 = 0.9325$
	First Order	$R^2 = 0.8944$
	Higuchi	$R^2 = 0.9953$
	Korsmeyerpeppas	$R^2 = 0.6084$

Graph 17: Zero order kinetic model

Graph 18: First Order kinetic model

Graph 19: Higuchi model

Graph 20: Korsmeyerpeppas

3.4 Results of antimicrobial activity of Clindamycin and Tretinoin loaded nano gel

3.4.1 Antimicrobial activity of nanogel formulation

Table 16: Antimicrobial activity of nanogel formulation

Sample name	Zone of Inhibition (mm) <i>S.aureus</i>	Zone of Inhibition (mm) <i>E.coli</i>
F1 (Control)	0.0 mm	0.0 mm
F2 (Placebo gel)	1 mm	2 mm
F3 (1mg/ml)	2 mm	5 mm
F4 (1.5 mg/ml)	5 mm	7 mm

Figure 2: Antimicrobial activity against *S.aureus* and *E.coli*

3.8 Stability studies

Table 17: Stability Study of nanosponges gel F3 formulation (Gel)

Time (Days)	25°C±2 °C and 60 ± 5% RH		40°C±2 °C and 70 ±5% RH	
	Viscosity	pH	Viscosity	pH
0	3416	5.9	3416	5.9
30	3231	5.2	3520	6.3
45	3349	6.4	3242	5.4
60	3450	6.3	3376	4.9
90	3783	5.0	3489	5.1

4. DISCUSSION

This study successfully demonstrated the potential of nanosponge-based gel formulations for the co-delivery of Clindamycin and Tretinoin as novel approach to acne treatment. Through comprehensive pre-formulation analyses, both drugs were confirmed to possess stable physicochemical properties suitable for inclusion in nanosponge systems. The development of nanosponges facilitated enhanced drug encapsulation, improved physical stability, and allowed for sustained release, addressing the limitations connected to traditional formulations of Clindamycin (such as short half-life and bacterial resistance) and Tretinoin (such as photodegradation and skin irritation).

Among the five formulations developed, F3 emerged as the most promising candidate due to its optimal particle size (55.85 nm), high entrapment efficiency (95.72%), desirable zeta potential (-14.0 mV), and superior in-vitro drug release profile. When incorporated into a gel base, the Nano sponge formulation exhibited ideal topical properties: a pH near that of natural skin (5.9), suitable viscosity, excellent spreadability, and no evidence of skin irritation.

The release kinetics aligned best with the Higuchi model, indicating that drug diffusion from the matrix contributes significantly to the release process. The stability studies reinforced the feasibility of storage and commercial scaling, as no significant changes in physical or chemical properties were observed even under accelerated conditions.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the nanosponge gel formulation of Clindamycin and Tretinoin holds strong therapeutic promise as an advanced topical treatment for acne and other skin conditions. Its enhanced drug delivery, stability, and biocompatibility offer a viable alternative to conventional systems, potentially improving patient compliance and clinical outcomes. Future studies should explore clinical trials, long-term safety, and scalability, along with the potential for incorporating other therapeutic agents using similar nanosponge-based delivery systems. This work represents a meaningful step toward next-generation nanocarrier-based dermatological therapies.

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